

Workshop on the refinement of the methodology for the HBM Guidance Values (HBM-GVs):

4th to 6th November 2020 – ANSES (virtual meeting)

Additional Deliverable Report

AD5.10

WP 5 - Translation of results into policy

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Abbreviations

ACGIH	American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists
AF _H	Assessment Factor accounting for intraspecies differences
ANSES	French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety
BAR	German biological reference values in the work area
BBzP	Butyl benzyl phthalate
BEI	Biological exposure indices
BGV	Biological Guidance Value
BLV	Biological Limit Value
BLW	German biological guidance values
BM	Biomarker
BMDL	Benchmark Dose (lower bound of the confidence interval)
BPA	Bisphenol A
BPS	Bisphenol S
BRV	Biological Reference Value
CLP	Classification, Labelling and Packaging
DBP	Di-n-butyl phthalate
DEHP	Di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate
DFG	German Research Foundation
DiBP	Diisobutyl phthalate
DINCH	1,2-cyclohexane dicarboxylic acid diisononyl ester
DMAC	Dimethylacetamide
DMF	Dimethylformamide
DPHP	Di(2-propylheptyl) phthalate
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
EKA	German exposure equivalents for carcinogenic substances
EU	European Union
FIOH	Finnish Institute of Occupational Health
F _{ue}	Urinary excretion factor
HBM	Human Biomonitoring
HBM4EU	European Human Biomonitoring Joint Programme
HBM-GV(s)	HBM Guidance Value(s)
HBM-GV _{GenPop}	HBM-GV for general population

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HBM-GV _{Worker}	HBM-GV for occupationally exposed adults
INRAE	French National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment,
MAK	Maximum Workplace Concentration (Maximale Arbeitsplatz-Konzentration)
NEP	1-ethylpyrrolidin-2-one
NMP	1-methyl-2-pyrrolidone
NO(A)EC	No Observed (Adverse) Effect Concentration
NO(A)EL	No Observed (Adverse) Effect Level
8h-OEL	Occupational Exposure Limit (for 8 hours)
OHAT	Office of Health Assessment and Translation of the U.S. National Toxicology Program
PBPK/PBTK	Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic/Toxicokinetic
PFAS	Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances
RAC	ECHA's Committee for Risk Assessment
RIVM	Netherlands National Institute for Public Health and the Environment
SCOEL	Scientific Committee on Occupational Exposure Limit Values
TK	Toxicokinetic
TLV-TWA	Threshold Limit Value-Time Weighted Average
TRV	Toxicity Reference Value
UBA	German Environment Agency
VITO	Flemish Institute for Technological Research

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1 Introduction

Within the framework of task 5.2 of the European Joint Programme, HBM4EU, human biomonitoring guidance values (HBM-GVs) are derived for HBM4EU priority substances.

The methodology applied to derive these values is described in the concept paper released in the HBM4EU task 5.2 workframe (HBM4EU concept paper) and published in a peer-reviewed journal (Apel et al., 2020).

For the time being, HBM-GVs are derived in HBM4EU under inclusion of experts from the 30 partner countries. Future use and implementation will be discussed among partners and the EU Commission but are without prejudice to existing or ongoing risk assessment work in order to inform EU policy-making.

Several HBM-GVs for the general and occupational population have already been derived for some phthalates and a substitute (DEHP, DPHP, DnBP, DiBP, BBzP, DINCH, see Lange et al., 2021), bisphenols (BPA (Ougier et al., 2021), BPS), cadmium (Lamkarkach et al., 2020) and recently for aprotic solvents (NEP, NMP, DMF, DMAC, see Deliverable D 5.9).

During the production and the consultation phases of the deliverables describing the derivation of such HBM-GVs, interesting questions were raised and valuable comments have been received. Some of these comments may justify a refinement of the methodology of the derivation of HBM-GVs as elaborated within HBM4EU by UBA and ANSES. Most of the HBM-GV proposals aimed to improve harmonization approaches for the two populations: general population and workers.

It was then decided within task 5.2 to organise a workshop that was initially aimed to take place at ANSES in spring 2020. However, due to the Covid-19 pandemic, the workshop was postponed and held virtually over three afternoons, from November 4th to 6th.

Topics that have been discussed are related to:

- How to address the differences between the derivation of HBM-GV_{GenPop} and HBM-GV_{worker}?
- Toxicokinetics and modelling aspects
- Selection of (exposure) biomarkers (BM) and matrices
- Level of confidence (LoC) associated to HBM-GVs
- How to deal with non-threshold substances in the occupational field?
- The current status of the strategy to evaluate HBM results for mixtures, exemplary for phthalates

In the current deliverable, a summary of the main discussions and proposals for the refinement of the methodology for the derivation of the HBM-GVs is reported. These proposals will be taken up in future HBM-GV derivations, if appropriate and feasible, and can be seen as optional to the methodology paper (Apel et al., 2020).

The workshop was audio recorded to facilitate the reporting of the workshop and for subsequent research activities. The audio files and transcripts are stored safely on a secured server and are only distributed among the organisers of the workshop.

In the first instance, a draft report of the workshop has been produced. Participants were given the opportunity to give feedback on this draft report. A final report has then been produced as part of a deliverable for HBM4EU that will be made public on the website after approval of the Management Board and the European Commission.

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2 Composition of the group of participants

Participants have been personally invited to this workshop, in a targeted way, to ensure that the group was not too large for the necessary interaction, but sufficiently diverse in composition. The intention was to invite experts having contributed to the derivation of HBM-GVs within task 5.2 by having provided comments on the released reports during the consultation phase. These experts on biomonitoring came from Europe and Canada. Some of these experts are not part of the HBM4EU consortium but were invited because of their involvement in the ANSES' Working Group on "Biomarkers of exposure" or their activities at international level such as OECD or in Canada. The list of participants is provided in Annex 1.

During the workshop, breakout group discussions were organized. The first aim of these sessions was to offer more opportunity for each participant to express her/his views. Indeed, because of time constraints, it was not possible to have such intensive discussions within the plenary group. The second aim was for the participants to share their views and examine from different angles the questions submitted to each session.

Before breakout group sessions, a short presentation of the points to be discussed was made in plenary as well as the questions were submitted to the breakout groups. Participants were then invited to raise questions if needed to clarify some points before breakout sessions. Each breakout group had to answer the same set of questions. In total 3 sub-groups were created in advance. The organisers tried to have in each sub-group a well-balanced composition of participants regarding either their fields of expertise and involvement in the HBM4EU project. A chair was assigned in advance for each subgroup to facilitate discussions, and a rapporteur from the ANSES team to help the chair for the reporting at the plenary sessions. Templates were provided to each chair and rapporteur to facilitate reporting and to harmonize the format for each subgroup.

The workshop program is included in Annex 2.

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3 Summary and conclusions

In this report a summary is provided for the different parts of the workshop. In a final chapter, we also have a summary of the main points that we agreed upon during the workshop and of those for which there are still diverging views. Thoughts on the way forward are also provided.

3.1 Summary and conclusions of day 1

On day 1, several presentations were made on the current methodology for the derivation of HBM-GV (as described in Apel et al., 2020) and a first short overview of the different points of discussions raised during the consultation phases of the HBM-GV reports, as described below, were also presented. In between the presentations, sufficient time was provided for questions and discussion. The presentations are included in Annex 3.

Then a **first breakout group discussion** of 45 minutes was organised, which was dedicated to the **differences between the derivation of HBM-GVs for the general population and workers**. The participants were divided in 3 subgroups and invited to answer questions related to:

- Differences in the selection of key studies for the general population *versus* workers (e.g. for a reprotoxic endpoint),
- Differences in the use of intraspecies factors (AF_H) for the general population *versus* workers (e.g. critical foetal exposure),

Differences in the relative contributions of the exposure routes between the general population and the workers, in case associated TK differences for the substance of interest are observed. Each subgroup reported their findings in plenary sessions followed by a final discussion.

On the basis of these presentations and the discussions, a few general conclusions can be formulated for each question.

1 Differences in the key studies selection

Regarding the HBM-GV_{worker} derivation based on a developmental toxic effect, is it legitimate to not consider key studies exposing animals throughout pregnancy and/or during lactation, considering that pregnant and breastfeeding women should not be exposed to developmental toxicants at their workplace from the 2nd pregnancy trimester on?

General agreement that studies exposing animals during the whole pregnancy as also during the perinatal period (for example lactation) should be considered for the derivation of HBM-GV for workers because:

- regulations in the various countries regarding developmental toxicants may differ and are not always implemented
- women may be back at work while still breast feeding
- in some countries social conditions do not always allow women to stop working when they are exposed to reprotoxic substances
- exposure during the first weeks of pregnancy (first trimester) may lead to a significant chronic exposure for long half-life compounds for the newborn: “body burden” concept
- some compounds with reproductive/developmental toxic effects are not assessed at EU level (CLP classification)

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To conclude, a compound by compound approach depending on the knowledge available on the critical window of susceptibility during *in utero* exposure should be applied.

2 Differences in the default AF_H

- *In case of a critical developmental toxic effect (in utero exposure), is a different value for the intraspecies assessment factor (AF_H) between the general population and the workers justified?*

- In general, unregarding the question of developmental effects, there is no scientific reason to differentiate AF_H between workers and general population except if there are data showing more sensitivity for young people or elderly
- It would be better to harmonize at EU level between sectorial regulations: biocides risk assessment already uses a factor of 10 for both general population and workers.
- For the time being, it could be more pragmatic to keep the default values (10 for the general population and 5 for workers)
- A factor of 10 is justified for both populations (general population and workers) for developmental effects to protect the foetus

- *Are there other critical effects or situations where the difference might be questionable?*

A factor of 10 may be justified for other effects: sensitization for example, as we can not be sure that workers are less vulnerable than the general population.

3 Differences in TK and potency according to the exposure routes

How to deal with TK and potency differences that depend on the exposure routes (as well as their variable relative contributions to the overall exposure)?

- Try to define the most realistic scenario of exposure (also with support from industry and worker associations) and if several ones are given, either select the most conservative or a range to reflect variabilities/uncertainties
- Workers are part of the general population and for BPA for example, it was not possible to differentiate between both routes of exposure (oral or dermal) – (as food exposure already overloads occupational exposure when looking at the total BPA in urine). The selected biomarker of exposure for BPA, i.e. urinary total BPA, does not allow to monitor BPA risky exposures at the workplace, which are likely occurring through skin exposure or inhalation, considering the high background levels of BPA that originate mostly from the non-occupational intake by individuals. Indeed, BPA absorbed by dermal contact or by inhalation directly enters the systemic circulation without undergoing first pass metabolism, generating higher blood ratios of free BPA (the toxicologically relevant species) over total BPA in comparison with the oral route.
- Use the skin notation to be alerted that a different approach can be used for the derivation of the HBM-GV but in which direction? To allocate a larger share to the dermal exposure in the derivation of the internal value or on the contrary, when workers will wear protective equipment, not to consider dermal route?
- As people wearing gloves are more exposed dermally (hairdressers, surgeons): constant exposure 8h due to gloves - by substances that migrate from the gloves to the skin – it would be useful to derive HBM-GV for this particular population.

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To close the first day, a presentation on **“How to deal with non-threshold substances in the occupational field (i.e. genotoxic carcinogens)”** was given during a plenary session followed by a general discussion.

First, an overview of the different approaches was presented, including the approach in the HBM4EU project but also the ones followed by SCOEL and RAC, ANSES, DFG and ACGIH.

In the HBM4EU initiative, no value is derived based on non-threshold effects for the general population. For workers, one option (bases on ANSES methodology) consists in performing a quantitative risk assessment with a scale of concentrations corresponding to additional lifetime risks (10^{-4} , 10^{-5} and 10^{-6}). Another option consists in deriving a value on the basis of a non-carcinogenic adverse effect. In both cases, the values cannot be considered as guidance values below which no health effect can occur. The RAC and formerly SCOEL, do not derive biological limit values (BLV) for non-treshold carcinogens, but only propose biological guidance values (BGV) corresponding to the upper background concentration of the chemical agent or one of its metabolites in any appropriate biological medium corresponding to a certain percentile (generally the 90th or 95th percentile) in a defined population which is not occupationally exposed.

For ANSES, the first option is to derive an 8h-OEL calculated on the basis of risk levels and the correlation of airborne and biomarker’s levels. If the data are insufficient, another option consists in deriving a pragmatic BLV based on the relationship between the biomarker’s concentration and another health effect with a threshold or based on correlation between atmospheric exposure and the biomarker’s concentration. Additionally, as for SCOEL/RAC, a biological reference value can also be proposed, based on the background levels in the general population (95th percentile).

The DFG proposes an Exposure Equivalent for Carcinogenic substances (EKA value) if a MAK value and a relationship between airborne concentration of the carcinogen and the biomarker level exists. Biological guidance values (BLW) can also be proposed by the DFG for non-carcinogenic effects of carcinogenic substances and for substances without sufficient data. The BLW values are intended to provide a basis for biomonitoring of exposed persons by the physician. At this level, risk of health impairment cannot be excluded. The DFG can also give reference values (BAR) based on the background level in a reference population of adults without occupational exposure to the agent (95th percentile).

ACGIH first assesses the feasibility of deriving values. Then if sufficient scientific evidence is available a biological exposure index (BEI) is developed, but no BEI is derived on non-threshold effects. For carcinogenic substances, BEIs are derived based on another occurring effect or based on TLV-TWA (8h-OEL) levels.

A summary of these different approaches is presented in the table 1.

Table 1: Comparison of the different international approaches for non-threshold substances biological values.

	HBM4EU	SCOEL/RAC	ANSES	DFG	ACGIH
Name of values	HBM-GV	BLV No Value for non threshold effect BGV	BLV Pragmatic BLV BRV	BLW EKA BAR	BEI No BEI for non threshold effect
Option 1	GenPop: No HBM-GV_{GenPop} Workers: RA: 10 ⁻⁴ , 10 ⁻⁵ and 10 ⁻⁶	-	RA: 10 ⁻⁴ , 10 ⁻⁵ and 10 ⁻⁶	EKA (correlation with MAK values)	BEI based on correlation with TLV-TWA
Option 2	GenPop: No HBM-GV_{GenPop} Workers: HBM-GV _{worker} based on an other effect	-	Pragmatic BLV based on an other effect	BLW	BEI based on an other effect
Background option*	No	BGV	BRV	BAR	No

When data are available, background values can be recommended if no health-based values for non-threshold substances are recommended (or in addition)

After the presentation of these approaches, the following questions were raised to launch the discussion:

- How can risk managers use these values (based on excess risk) for workers?
- Could these approaches also be applied for the general population?
- How could biomarkers of effects be used to derive guidance values for non-threshold substances?

It was mentioned that if there is an EU-wide binding occupational exposure limit value for a substance, it would be useful from the usability point of view to have a biological limit value which corresponds to that 8h-OEL. In addition, we could have another more science-based value for example based on risk levels.

Regarding the 3rd question, the effect biomarkers are indicating the integrative effect of all compounds having the same mode of action, so we could translate the result of an effect

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biomarker *via* a reference compound to a toxic equivalent concentration. It could be an option in the future, if we want to have an integrative assessment. With the background effect biomarker levels, it could be easy to identify an occupational exposure to a genotoxic agent.

It could also be interesting, for the same substances, where possible, to compare values based on excess of risk and the pragmatic values.

In both cases, the risk managers should be educated on the uncertainties and the meaning of these values.

3.2 Summary and conclusions of day 2

A **second breakout group** discussion was organised which was dedicated to the **selection of exposure biomarker and matrices** in the derivation of HBM-GV for the general population and for workers. During 45 minutes the participants were divided in 3 subgroups and invited to answer questions related to:

- Biomarker(s) selection: criteria for exposure (biomarker(s), one or more biomarkers, route of exposure)
- Matrix selection: criteria for matrix selection, one or more matrices, sampling and analytical methods

Reports from each subgroup were then done in the plenary session followed by a final discussion.

On the basis of these presentations and the discussions, a few general conclusions can be formulated for each question.

What is the reasoning to select a biomarker?

More than one biomarker: what are the advantages and disadvantages?

Focus has been made on biomarkers in blood during the discussions although urine is also frequently used as a matrix due to non invasive sampling methods.

- Blood is often the best matrix because it represents systemic exposure at the target organs. Sometimes using whole blood has an advantage over plasma or serum because it covers all the components of blood, including (e.g., proteins, erythrocytes, platelets) and therefore, there is a high chance of detection
- Blood samplings may pose ethical issues compared to urine in the general population but seem to be better accepted in some countries (Netherlands-PFAS, France-lead, Canada – CHMS project for general population),
- Blood is not appropriate for compounds (e.g. essential elements) for which homeostasis mechanisms apply; in these cases urine is better: zinc, molybdenum, copper...
- Depends on the TK of the compounds: if substances show short half lives, blood may not be relevant (except possibly if high frequency of exposure occurs), in particular for the general population.
- Analytical methods for blood may not be accurate or sample contamination due to ubiquitous presence in laboratory analysis and sample collection materials would decrease data quality and reliability (e.g. Aluminium).

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Tiered approach:

- First look at a pragmatic biomarker (BM), based on analytical considerations (e.g. total BPA in urine) and if we can not exclude a risk then measure a more toxicologically relevant BM (e.g. free BPA in blood) or the other way round?
- First select the best BM in terms of toxicity and if there is no available or reliable analytical method to measure it, then move to the 2nd best one.

One versus several metabolites as BM

- Tiered approach: first, assess the exposure considering all metabolites and if necessary look in more detail at concentrations of the active compound(s)
- Different metabolites depending on exposure route, e.g. phthalates. Focusing on one metabolite can be more specific for one route than for a specific population.
- Proportion between metabolites may also differ across different matrices. E.g. Urinary cadmium reflects long term exposure vs blood = short term exposure.
- Possible if enough data for several metabolites are available. Some limit values defined for a set of metabolites -> variability across countries (not similar measurements).
- The selection of 2 metabolites as BM allows to reduce interindividual variability or on the contrary increases it?

Different analytical and toxicological preference(s) for selection: Is it a trade-off between analysis and toxicology?

- Depends on substances and objectives (exposure or risk): case by case basis.
- If risk drives assessment then choose a toxicologically relevant BM.
- If exposure drives assessment then choose a more representative BM of the exposure scenario.
- Pragmatic approach: BM driven by analytical capacities and wait until good methods available to measure more toxicologically relevant BM.

The analytical methods should be sensitive enough to capture fluctuations of exposure. There is a trade-off between already available analytical methods and the need to develop new methods to capture a more toxicologically relevant biomarker.

Correction for diuresis

Is correction for diuresis needed? Should correction for diuresis always be investigated (compare corrected vs uncorrected)? Methods for correction (established versus potential)?

- Look at the substance TK and the excretion mechanism of the BM to distinguish the best suitable method to measure its urinary concentration.
- If we don't have enough TK data to decide, then both values could be proposed: corrected and not corrected.
- For the adjustment, up to now, creatinine is more often used but it depends on some parameters such as: food regimen (meat), age, phenotypes... Specific gravity is more and more used, less variability but still influenced by some common chronic diseases such as diabetes; need more data to switch from creatinine adjustment to specific gravity but it will probably be the case within few years ...

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- HBM-GV should reflect the variability in urine volume excretion, probabilistic approach and range could then be justified

A presentation on “**How to improve the level of confidence associated to HBM-GVs**” was then presented during a plenary session followed by a general discussion.

The levels of confidence (LoC) attributed to derived HBM-GVs are relying on expert judgment. Individual criteria are examined and a confidence level (high, medium or low) is assigned to each criterion. Then an overall level of confidence is given to the HBM-GV derived by equally combining the levels of individual criteria (for more details please see Apel et al., 2020). The option chosen for deriving the HBM-GV directly influences the overall level of confidence attributed. For example, values derived by considering human epidemiological data will be attributed a higher level of confidence than values derived relying on results obtained solely from animal studies.

Individual criteria examined include:

- the nature and quality of the data available (epidemiological data available; animal data in more than one species) and if it covers different effects, exposure times and exposure windows;
- the choice of the critical effect, the likelihood of its transferability from animal species to humans, the substance mode of action;
- the quality of the key study supported by validated tools (e.g. OHAT approach for epidemiological studies or ToxRtool or Scirap for animal studies);
- the choice of the critical dose (point of departure), e.g. whether it is a BMDL, a NOAEL(/C) or a LOAEL(/C), and the quality of the dose-response relationship (e.g. the number of doses tested in the study or difference in concentration between the tested doses);
- the nature of the extrapolation across and within species, e.g. the use of a quality PBTK model or of default values accounting for intra- and inter-species extrapolations;

Two main elements for assessing the confidence in the derived HBM-GVs are highlighted:

- the understanding of the relationship between the measured biomarker and the critical or relevant target tissue dose metric;
- the robustness of the available toxicokinetic data and PBK models when they are used.
- Participants were invited to discuss the following questions:
- The attribution of a low level of confidence can highlight the data gaps and thereby reflects the accuracy of the value. However a low level of confidence does not necessarily mean a low level of protection, especially because the HBM-GV derivation is generally based on very conservative scenarios and default assumptions leading to a conservative value. Therefore, is it necessary to consider these 2 dimensions for the attribution of the confidence level?
- Can we consider a probabilistic approach for the derivation of HBM-GVs (with a distribution of parameters)?

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Discussions led to the following conclusions:

- If a good and consistent dataset is available i.e regarding the toxicity reference value, the urinary fraction and the urinary flow rate, a probabilistic approach can be considered and a HBM-GV could be proposed with a confidence interval or a range including both uncertainties and the population variability.
- However, it was raised that such a probabilistic approach is not always easily applicable in terms of communication to the risk managers that needs to be educated on how to use a range or a distribution of values and that a deterministic value is often more practical at workplaces. This also requires a detailed discussion with risk managers on the benefits of this approach giving them the room to discuss the measures that need to be taken.
- If a probabilistic approach is followed, then all data could be included in the distribution and reflect uncertainty/variability.

Risk managers need to be educated to the probabilistic approach, it will help them to mitigate between cost/benefits.

A third breakout group discussion was then organised which was dedicated to **toxicokinetics** considerations **and modelling aspects** when deriving HBM-GVs. During 45 minutes the participants were divided in 3 subgroups and invited to answer questions related to:

- How to deal with short elimination half-life substances, when steady-state is not reached?
- The assumption of constant exposure for short half-life substances exposing humans in real life rather by peaks of exposure (e.g. BPA), when estimating an HBM-GV equivalent to an external dose
- The impact of the potential variability of the urinary excretion factor (F_{ue}) of the selected biomarker depending on inter-individual characteristics (e.g. age, gender, TK differences)
- The reasons for the use of a F_{ue} measured either at 24h or 48h after the substance intake, in a mass-balance equation for calculating an HBM-GV.

Reports from each subgroup were then done in a plenary session followed by a final discussion.

On the basis of these presentations and the discussions, a few general conclusions can be formulated for each question.

Is the assumption of a steady-state exposure correct when using the mass balance approach? If not what could be a better approach?

Steady-state exposure depends on the half-life of the compound and the dosing interval

- For workers: assumption of continuous exposure during the shift is appropriate
- For the general population: it is more difficult to consider a continuous exposure; but this can be the case for some substances that are present in various media (dust, drinking water, diet...) and are likely to be taken up constantly. This should be treated on a case-by-case basis. For example, general population expose to metals primarily through diet. So, continuous exposure could be expected even with short half-life (e.g. Molybdenum). For some of the other substances with short half-life and exposure only through consumer products, steady-state may not be reached, if the product is not used daily.

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- For compounds with very short half-lives, it is better to have 24h urine samples (but more complex in practice); if not it is very difficult to interpret spot urine values; for BPA: very high interindividual variability; current studies pooling several spot samples to have a representative daily urinary concentration may be of some interest
- For workers, definition of tasks is also important to select the sampling time.

How to select the best value for the urinary excretion factor (F_{ue})? 24h or 48h? Male and/or female, Ages? How to express uncertainties around this factor?

- It would be better to differentiate between gender/ages, etc., but it is difficult to have a representative sample of the population in volunteer studies.
- 24h or 48h? The molar F_{ue} reflects the molar ratio between the the urinary excreted amount of biomarker and the amount of parent compound taken up. Thus, the best is to have the most excreted quantity of the metabolites explaining why calculating the F_{ue} at 48h could be needed in some cases depending of the half-life of the biomarker; as the F_{ue} will be higher at 48h compared to 24h, then the HBM-GV will also be higher and then less protective but more accurate.
- When a polymorphism induces differences in the metabolism/excretion, a differentiation in the F_{ue} should be taken into account, but having different values for different sub-populations can be confusing.
- If a probabilistic approach is followed then all data could be included in the distribution and reflect uncertainty/variability.

Which exposure pattern should be assumed when estimating the concentration of the exposure biomarker corresponding to an external exposure guidance value?

- Ideally, external exposure based on the protocol of the key study should be used to model the internal value in the animal (blood and urine) and then decide which is the best BM, and based on a human PBPK model simulate different reasonable scenarios of exposure (e.g. for general population continuous or 3 times per day via oral route, or 50/50 oral/dermal or ...) and see what would be the more appropriate value
- The HBM-GV should try to cover all scenarios

3.3 Summary and conclusions of day 3

Only plenary sessions were organised on the last day of the workshop.

This third day started with a dedicated session on how HBM-GVs could be used for mixture risk assessments (MRA).

In 2017-2020, HBM-GVs for five phthalates, namely DEHP, DiBP, DnBP, DPHP and BBzP were derived for the general and the working population. One task for T5.2 was to propose a strategy for a cumulative risk assessment for phthalates as an exemplary class of compounds. For this, a workshop with HBM4EU experts from WP15, WP14, WP5 and also external experts was planned in May 2020. Due to the travel restrictions as a result of the pandemic this workshop had to be postponed. For this reason, the workshop on a strategy for using HBM-GV in a MRA was rescheduled to be back-to-back to the workshop of T5.2 on the refinement of the methodology.

A discussion paper on the strategy for using HBM-GVs for a MRA on reprotoxic phthalates was prepared and distributed to the participants for review beforehand. The main aim of this workshop

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was to discuss the methodological approach and the selection of substances for which a MRA could be done. After the workshop, the strategy will be refined and published in a peer-reviewed journal. Further, this approach can optionally be implemented by WP10 partners, if resources are available and results of Task 8.1 (Alignment of studies) are available in due time and the data gathered allows for it.

The strategy was briefly presented. In the plenary sessions it was discussed, whether the approach is useful; if the selected compounds for a possible mixture risk assessment for the group of phthalates is reasonable and if the derived HBM-GV for DiNP for the MRA only is appropriate. An in-depth discussion took place on which endpoints are appropriate to be selected for phthalates in order to perform a MRA. The proposed HBM-GV for DiNP, which is based on the EFSA TDI was evaluated to be not appropriate and needs to be adapted. Testosterone suppression as common endpoint for the phthalate syndrome was agreed among the participants.

The strategy will be adapted according to the suggestions made on the workshop as well as the written review on the discussion paper. After publication, the strategy will be made public on the HBM4EU Website.

Finally, to open the discussion to some on-going initiatives related to the derivation of HBM-GVs a presentation was given by Robert Pasanen-Kase on "Occupational Biomonitoring activity for OECD Working Party on Hazard Assessment (WPHA) and Working Party on Exposure Assessment (WPEA) & collaboration with ISES Europe HBM group. This presentation was followed by a short discussion on how to move forward.

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Ougier E, Ganzleben C, Lecoq P, Bessems J, David M, Schoeters G, Lange R, Meslin M, Uhl M, Kolossa-Gehring M, Rousselle C, Lobo Vicente J. 2021. Chemical prioritisation strategy in the European Human Biomonitoring Initiative (HBM4EU) – Development and results. *International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health* 236.

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5 Annex 1: List of participants

Name	Institution
Rousselle Christophe	ANSES, FR
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Robert Pasanen-Kase	State Secretariat for Economic Affairs (SECO), CH
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6 Annex 2: Agenda

Task 5.2 : Workshop on the refinement of the methodology for the HBM-GVs derivation

November 4th-6th, 2020 – ANSES (virtual meeting)

Day 1 – November 4th, 2020

13:00-13:10	Opening and welcome
13:10-13:45	<u>Presentation of the current methodology for the derivation of HBM-GV developed under HBM4EU.</u>
13:45-14:00	<u>Overview of the different points of discussion raised during the consultation phases of the HBM-GV reports.</u>
14:00-15:45	<p><u>How to address the differences between the derivation of HBM-GVGenPop and HBM-GVworker ?</u></p> <p>1/ Presentation of the topics : (15')</p> <p>2/ Discussion in subgroups of experts (45')</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Differences in the key studies selection due to differences of the targeted population and exposure scenarios. - In case of <u>a reprotoxic effect</u> (<i>in utero</i> exposure) selected as critical effect for deriving the HBM-GVs, is the difference in AF_H justified? - Are there other critical effect where the difference might be questionable? - How to deal with TK and potency difference depending on the exposure routes (and their relative contributions to the overall exposure)? - <p>3/ Reporting of discussions and closing discussion (45')</p>
15:45-16:00	Break

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16:00-16:45	<p><u>How to deal with non-threshold substances in the occupational field (i.e. genotoxic carcinogens)?</u></p> <p>1/ Presentation of the topics (15')</p> <p>2/ Discussions and closing (30')</p>
16:45-17:00	Sum-up and closing
Day 2 – November 5th, 2020	
13:00-13:10	Opening and welcome
13:10-14:55	<p><u>Biomarker and matrix selection</u></p> <p>1/ Presentation of the topics : (15')</p> <p>2/ Discussion in subgroups of experts (45')</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Biomarker(s) selection: criteria for exposure (biomarker(s), one or more biomarkers, route of exposure - Matrix selection: criteria for matrix selection, one or more matrices, sampling and analytical methods <p>3/ Reporting of discussions and closing discussion (45')</p>
14:55-15:40	<p><u>How to improve the setting of levels of confidence associated to HBM-GVs?</u></p> <p>1/ Presentation of the topics (15')</p> <p>2/Discussions and closing (30')</p>
15:40-15:55	Break

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15:55-17:40	<p><u>Toxicokinetics and modelling aspects</u></p> <p>1/ Presentation of the topics (15') :</p> <p>2/ Discussion in subgroups of experts (45')</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What impact could a steady state assumption in using the urinary mass balance approach have on the derived HBM-GV value? - Should the F_{ue} estimated at 24h or at 48h be used preferably, when the external dose is given <i>per day</i> (e.g. $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}/\text{day}$) or a <i>daily</i> urinary flow rate adjusted to the bw is the denominator of the mass balance equation? - How to assess the potential variability of the F_{ue} of the selected exposure biomarker(s), depending on the inter-individual characteristics between the PK study volunteers and the target population (e.g. age, gender, differences in metabolism)? - Which exposure pattern should be assumed when estimating the concentration of the exposure biomarker corresponding to an external exposure guidance value? <p>3/ Reporting of discussions and closing discussion (45')</p>
17:40-17:55	Sum-up and closing
Day 3 – November 6th, 2020	
13:00-13:10	Opening and welcome
13:10-15:10	<u>Current status of the strategy to evaluate HBM results for mixtures, exemplary for phthalates.</u>
15:10:-15:20	Break
15:20-15:45	<u>Summary of workshop discussions</u>
15:45-16:45	<p><u>Where do we go from here?</u></p> <p>-Occupational Biomonitoring activity for OECD Working Party on Hazard Assessment (WPHA) and Working Party on Exposure Assessment (WPEA) & collaboration with ISES Europe HBM group.</p> <p>-Round table : What could be the next steps at EU level of the HBM-GV ?</p>
16:45-17:00	Wrap-up and acknowledgment

7 Annex 3: Presentations

7.1 Introduction

WP4: Prioritization of substances

WP4: Priorisation des substances & workplan

 First round**Priorisation 2016**

9 substance groups:

1. **Phthalates/DINCH**
2. **Bisphenols**
3. Per-/Polyfluorinated compounds
4. Flame Retardants
5. **Cadmium & Chromium**
6. PAHs and air pollutants
7. Anilin family: MOCA
8. Chemical mixtures
9. Emerging chemicals

 Second round**Priorisation 2018**

9 substance groups:

1. Acrylamide
2. **Aprotic solvents**
3. Arsenic
4. Diisocyanites
5. Lead
6. Mercury
7. Mycotoxines
8. Pesticides
9. UV filters

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Science policy

Policy questions

- What is the current exposure of the EU population?
- Are exposures different between countries? Why?
- Can we detect a significant decrease in levels after REACH?
- **Are exposure levels above any health relevant health assessment values?**
- Should the substance be subject to (further) regulation ?

Science → Policy (lead: VITO)

1. Health based guidance values
2. Improve risk assessment strategies
3. HBM based indicators to follow spatial and time trends
4. Participative and deliberative process to translate results in policy options

Buekers et al, Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health 2018, 15, 2085

Louro et al, Int. J of Hyg. Env. health, Ehttps://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2019.05.009

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**Thank you very
much
for your attention!**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 733032.

7.2 Presentation of the current methodology for the derivation of HBM-GV developed in HBM4EU

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Task 5.2 workshop Nov. 2020

HBM guidance values
**Reason for derivation, strategy,
results and ongoing activities**

Petra Apel

Reason to derive HBM- GVs within HBM4EU

- Growing number of uniformly collected biomonitoring data on various chemicals (metabolites) in human blood or urine, **but**
 - not always consistent and comparable toxicological evaluation at European level
 - Limited perception of HBM data and their assessments for chemicals regulation

Source: angelabrown/Patalia.com

- **Need for** easily applicable tools and guidance for harmonized evaluation of chemicals' body burden

Source: www.europekante.org

- **Benefit: HBM-based support of policy makers** for risk management and prioritized action

HBM4EU task 5-2 workshop, Nov. 04-06, 2020

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Underlying ideas for task 5.2

A **strategy should be established by consensus** within HBM4EU to derive health-related human biomonitoring guidance values (HBM-GVs)

- for priority substances in blood and/or urine thus integrating all exposure routes and being directly comparable with measured values
- for the general population and workers
- initially only project-related, but with a view to further use

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Task 5.2 procedure

A general strategy was established based on approaches of

- the German HBM Commission (HBM-I values)
- ANSES (Biological Limit Values - BLVs)
- Summit Toxicology/Health Canada (Biomonitoring Equivalents – BEs)

Apel P, Rousselle C, Lange R, Sissoko F, Kolossa-Gehring M, Ougier E (2020) Human biomonitoring initiative (HBM4EU) - Strategy to derive human biomonitoring guidance values (HBM-GVs) for health risk assessment. *International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health* 230, 113622

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Task 5.2 procedure

A literature search should be carried out for each substance to be able to derive up-to-date values.

Comments from a consultation should be considered.

- New values or
- Refinements of already existing values (often new information on toxicokinetic aspects, but also more current information on toxicity or even revised TDIs etc.)

Definition & Consequences of HBM-GVs' exceedances

HBM-GV_{GenPop}

Conc. at/below which there is no risk of health impairment anticipated

Exposure > HBM-GV

- identification of possible sources of exposure
- specific follow up examination of population's health status
- assessment whether risk management is necessary

HBM-GV_{Worker}

Conc. aimed to protect workers exposed regularly & over the course of a working life from adverse effects related to medium- and long-term exposure

Exposure > HBM-GV

- enhanced surveillance
- in case of exceedances on several occasions or in the majority of workers at the same workplace: cause must be investigated and proper reduction measures taken

Prerequisites for the derivation of HBM-GVs

Epidemiological data, toxicity reference values or toxicological data to select a critical concentration or dose

Reliable toxicokinetic information for humans and also for animals

Analytical traceability of the selected specific biomarker(s)

Effects - options to chose

- Take human data based on internal concentration and health effects relationship

Not available, not adequate regarding quality and focus or not current

- Rely on a toxicity reference value (e.g. ADI, TDI, TWI, reliable DNEL)
- For workers preferably on an occupational exposure limit (e.g. 8h-OEL, MAK value)

Not available, or not current

- Take data from experimental animal studies, decide on relevant critical effect and POD

Toxicokinetics – options and limitations

External dose has to be converted to corresponding internal matrix concentration of substance or metabolite(s)

- **Studies with human volunteers (factor for metabolic conversion – F_{ue}) → urinary mass balance approach**
Data on metabolite excretion often only from few volunteers, sex or age-specific differences or dependency on exposure levels are often not considered

Calculation HBM-GV:
high intra- and interindividual variation of urinary flow rate
- **PBPK/PBTK modeling**
models are mostly not available

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Global level of confidence (LoC) for uncertainties in data base – high - medium - low

- Nature and quality of the toxicological data
- Choice of critical effect
- Choice of key study
- Choice of POD
- Regarding extrapolations across and within species

But low level of confidence for the data base does not mean a low level of protection.

Protective approach based on conservative scenarios and default assumptions, e.g. life long exposure

Consolidated HBM-GVs for priority substances

Substance/ population group	Effect	POD	Toxico- kinetic data	Overall Level of Confidence
DEHP/GenPop	Male developmental impairment	TDI	Fue	Medium
Workers	Aspermatogenesis (Reprotoxicity)	NOAEL	Fue	Medium
DINCH/ GenPop	Nephrotoxicity	TDI	Fue	Medium
DPHP/GenPop	Effects on thyroid gland	RfD based on BMDL10	Fue	Low
Workers		RfD on BMDL10	Fue	Low
DnBP/GenPop	Delayed germ cell dev./ male mammary gland changes	DNEL	Fue	Medium
Workers	Reduction foetal testosterone	NOAEL	Fue	Medium

Consolidated HBM-GVs for priority substances

Substance/ population group	Effect	POD	Toxico- kinetic data	Overall LoC
DiBP/ GenPop	Delayed germ cell dev./ male mammary gland changes, 25% pot. diff	DNEL	Fue	Low
Worker	Reduction of foetal testosterone Read across with DnBP, 25 % pot. diff.	NOAEL		Low
BBzP/ GenPop/ Worker	Suppression of foetal testicular testosterone production/reduction of serum testosterone and reduced sperm count and motility	LOAEL	Fue	Medium
Cd/GenPop	Renal toxicity, low molecular weight proteinuria (LMWP) markers like beta-2-microglobulin (β 2M) and retinol-binding protein (RBP)	Human data, BMDL ₅	PBPK modeling	High
Cd/Worker		Human data, BMDL ₅	PBPK modeling	High-Medium

Consolidated HBM-GVs for priority substances

Substance/ population group	Effect	POD	Toxico- kinetic data	Overall LoC
BPA/ GenPop	Increased relative mean kidney weight in F0 male adults	t-TDI	modified PBPK model of Karrer et al. 2018	Medium
BPS/GenPop/ workers	Increased number of terminal end buds in the mammary gland, dose dependent increase in ductal area in the mammary gland, neurobehavioral toxicity	NOAEL	modified PBPK model of Karrer et al. 2018	Medium- low
BPF	-	-	-	-
NMP/GenPop	Developmental toxicity	NOAEL	Fue	Medium
NEP/GenPop	Developmental toxicity	NOAEL	Fue	Medium- low

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Ongoing activities

- Solvents: DMF, DMAC (workers; consultation ongoing)
- Pesticides: Deltamethrin (GenPop),
Cyfluthrin (GenPop)
- Mercury
- Chromium VI (Workers)

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**Thank you very much
for your attention!**
Many thanks also to the colleagues of
the task 5.2 team and all the
colleagues who commented on our
proposals

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 733032.

7.3 Overview of the different points of discussion raised during the consultation phases of the HBM-GV reports.

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Task 5.2 workshop Nov. 2020

Overview of the different points of discussion raised during the consultation phases of the HBM-GV reports.

Matthieu Meslin

Investigate, evaluate, protect

HBM-GVs development process

HBM4EU task 5.2 workshop, Nov 04-06, 2020

Petra Apol (UBA)

Consultation phase

Comments received from :

- EU Policy Board : EFSA, EU Commission (DG empl)...
- Many institutions from 17 National Hubs :

- Austria	- Croatia
- Belgium	- Israel
- Cyprus	- Slovenia
- Lithuania	- Slovakia
- Spain	- Netherlands
- Switzerland	- Germany
- Portugal	- France
- Finland	- UK
- Norway	

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1 – Examples of general comments on the derivation strategy

- The separation between exposure of the general population and workers is not always needed. Many of **the specific consideration for the workers also apply in general.**
- The derivation of HBM-GVs is **ambitious**; (*Option 2 has already a lot of uncertainty. Option 3 is going beyond that.*)
- What does concretely mean **“medium, low or high” confidence** for a calculated value in terms of human (individual) health ? in terms of public health ? in terms of risk management ?
- **ED effects could be non-threshold.** Setting up a limit is a (political) second step. This should be taken into account in the biomonitoring documents.

2 – Specific comments during HBM-GVs developments

- **Selected exposure biomarker(s)**
 - More precision is required to justify their selection(s).
 - Justification/advantage of selecting **several** exposure biomarkers **versus one** to derive an internal guide value?
 - Difference in **conjugation between the different routes** of exposure: relevance of measuring the total urinary fraction of the biomarker selected versus the free (active) fraction in the blood?
- **Toxicokinetics aspects**
 - **Use of the urinary excretion factor F_{UE} :**
 - « Please reflect potential under- or overestimations by taking a default F_{UE} independent of age, gender, and other toxicokinetic and toxicodynamic differences »
 - « Motivate the choice of an F_{UE} for 24h instead of 48h or vice versa »
 - **Impact of a steady state assumption in using mass balance approach on the derived HBM-GV value?**

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2 – Specific comments during HBM-GVs developments

• Specific questions on the derivation of a HBM-GV for workers.

- **Clarification requested on the conditions of exposure in the workplace and the description of the exposure scenarios.**
- **How can the various exposure situations and routes of exposure be taken into account when the biomarker of exposure selected is not the most relevant with regard to health effects (example of BPA)?**
- **Values adapted by sector of activity? Generic values?**
- **Should different key studies be selected for workers due to differences of the targeted population and exposure scenarios?**

Ex : Key studies investigated with late gestation + perinatal (breastfeeding) exposure considered irrelevant for the occupational sector?

- **Use of an intraspecies uncertainty factor of 5 for an effect involving in utero exposure (i.e. critical fetal exposure)**

Are there scientific arguments for considering a TK/TD difference in the fetal development of a mother exposed through her environment versus a mother exposed in the workplace?

Topics to be discussed during this workshop

Nov 4:

- How to address the differences between the derivation of HBM-GV_{GenPop} and HBM-GV_{worker} ?
- How to deal with non-threshold substances in the occupational field (i.e. genotoxic carcinogens)?

Nov 5

- Biomarker and matrix selection
- How to improve the setting of levels of confidence associated to HBM-GVs?
- Toxicokinetics and modelling aspects

Nov 6

- Current status of the strategy to evaluate HBM results for mixtures, exemplary for phthalates.
- Where do we go from here ?

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7.4 How to address the differences between the derivation of HBM-GV_{GenPop} and HBM-GV_{worker}?

T5.2 - Workshop on the refinement of the methodology for the HBM-GVs derivation
November 4th - 6th - ANSES (virtual meeting)

First sub-group work session :

How to address the differences between the derivation of HBM-GV_{GenPop} and HBM-GV_{worker} ?

1

T5.2 - Workshop on the refinement of the methodology for the HBM-GVs derivation
November 4th - 6th - ANSES (virtual meeting)

1 - Differences between the HBM-GV_{GenPop} and HBM-GV_{worker} derivation

Points of discussion :

- 1 - Differences in the key studies selection
- 2 - Differences in the default AF_H
- 3 - Differences in TK and thus possible potency according to the exposure routes

2

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1st point of discussion: differences in the key study selection

In certain cases, a different key study might be retained for deriving HBM-GVs between the general population and the working population, considering specificities related to :

- 1 - the target population (general population *versus* adult of working age)
- 2 - to the occupational exposure scenario

3

⇒ **Example of studies that might not be considered relevant for the HBM-GV_{worker} derivation :**

- Epidemiological studies conducted in the general population including very young or elderly people;
- Toxicological studies exposing animals at the premature or juvenile stage, or at an elderly age;
- **Toxicological studies exposing pregnant animals throughout pregnancy and/or the perinatal period**

indeed where the selected critical effect is developmental reprotoxicity, it has been considered that pregnant and breastfeeding women should not be exposed to reprotoxicant at their workplace, as soon as they become aware of their pregnancy (most often before the end of the 1st trimester)

⇒ **Selection of key studies for the HBM-GV_{worker} derivation in which animals are exposed only during the gestational period that corresponds to the human 1st trimester of pregnancy**

! Consideration based on EU-dependant regulations regarding reprotoxicant at the workplace !

➤ **Is this assumption appropriate for the HBM-GV_{worker} derivation?**

4

2nd point of discussion: difference in the intraspecies AF

The adjustment factor accounting for the intraspecies differences (AF_H), when set by default is according to ECHA guidance* at :

- $AF_H = 10$ for the general population
- $AF_H = 5$ for workers, considering that workers are a more homogenous population compared to the general population in that it should not include very young, very old or sick people.

- However, in case of a reprotoxic effect (*in utero* exposure) selected as critical effect for deriving the HBM-GVs, is this difference in AF_H justified?
- Are there other critical effect or situations where the difference might be questionable ?

* https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/13632/information_requirements_r8_en.pdf/e153243a-0310-44c5-8808-88af66223258

3rd point of discussion:

How to deal with TK and potency differences that depends on the exposure routes (and the variable relative contributions of the different exposure routes to the overall exposure)?

BPA example: derivation of the HBM-GV_{GenPop}

T5.2 - Workshop on the refinement of the methodology for the HBM-GVs derivation
 November 4th - 6th - ANSES (virtual meeting)
 I - Differences between the HBM-GV_{Oral} and HBM-GV_{Dermal} derivation

In short

Population group	Free BPA in plasma obtained after a 24h-averaged 100% oral exposure to the t-TDI of 4 µg/kg bw	Corresponding total BPA concentration in urine	
		Assuming a 100% oral BPA exposure	Assuming a 100% dermal BPA exposure
Adult (70 kg)	6.8.10 ⁻³ µg/L	233 µg/L	6.2 µg/L

Mixed oral/dermal scenarios depending on the relative contribution of each exposure routes (adult, 70 kg)

Relative contributions of the oral and dermal routes of exposure to the overall BPA exposure, generating the same free BPA concentration in plasma than a 24h-averaged oral exposure at the t-TDI (4 µg BPA/kg bw)		Corresponding estimated total BPA concentration in urine
% of oral exposure	% of dermal exposure	
100%	-	233 µg/L
90%	10%	215 µg/L
80%	20%	191 µg/L
70%	30%	165 µg/L
-	100%	6.2 µg/L

T5.2 - Workshop on the refinement of the methodology for the HBM-GVs derivation
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T5.2 - Workshop on the refinement of the methodology for the HBM-GVs derivation
November 4th - 6th - ANSES (virtual meeting)
I - Differences between the HBM-GV_{oral} and HBM-GV_{dermal} derivation

Summary of questions

1 - Differences in the key studies selection

Regarding the HBM-GV_{critical} derivation based on a developmental effect in the offspring, is it legitimate to not consider key studies exposing animals throughout pregnancy and/or during lactation by considering that pregnant and breastfeeding women should not be exposed to reprotoxicant at their workplace from the moment their pregnancy is declared (most often > 2nd pregnancy trimester on)?

2 - Differences in the default AF_H

- In case of a critical reprotoxic effect (*in utero* exposure) is a different value for the AF_H between the general population and the workers justified?
- Are there other critical effects or situations where the difference might be questionable?

3 - Differences in TK and potency according to the exposure routes

How to deal with TK and potency differences that depends on the exposure routes (as well as their variable relative contributions to the overall exposure)?

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7.5 How to deal with non-threshold substances in the occupational field (i.e. genotoxic carcinogens)?

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HBM guidance values
WP 5, Task 5.2

**How to deal with non-threshold
substances in the occupational
field ?**

Farida Lamkarkach & Jos Bessems

UBA

anses
Investigare, evaluare, protect

Overview of international approaches

- HBM4EU project**
 - Human Biomonitoring for Europe
- SCOEL and RAC:**
 - European Scientific Committee of Occupational Exposure Limit (SCOEL) and Risk assessment Committee (RAC) of the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA)
- ANSES**
 - French Agency for Food, Occupational and Environmental Health
- DFG**
 - Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft DFG - Germany
- ACGIH**
 - American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists - USA

HBM4EU Project – Europe

HBM-GV for the General Population and Workers

General population

- “ For the time being, if no effect threshold can be identified, e.g. for genotoxic carcinogens, HBM-GVGenPop are not proposed for the general population.”

No value for non-threshold effect

Workers

- 1st option: Quantitative risk assessment (RA) can be performed (→ scale of concentrations corresponding to additional lifetime risks 10^{-1} , 10^{-5} and 10^{-6})
- 2nd option: derivation on the basis of a non-carcinogenic adverse effect

These values can not be considered as guidance values below which no health effect occurs

Apel P, Rousselle C, Lange R, Sissoko F, Kolassa-Gehring M, Dugier E (2020) Human biomonitoring initiative (HBM4EU) Strategy to derive human biomonitoring guidance values (HBM-GVs) for health risk assessment. *International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health* 230, 113622

SCOEL and RAC - Europe

Since the end of the 1990s

BLV not derived for non-threshold carcinogens

Biological guidance Value (BGV)

- « Upper concentration of the chemical agent or one of its metabolites in any appropriate biological medium corresponding to a certain percentile (generally the 90th or 95th percentile) in a defined population »
- **Occupationally non-exposed group**

Acrylamide
CLP classification: Carc.1B and Mut.1B

Recommendations from the Scientific Committee on Occupational Exposure Limits for acrylamide	
Exposure limit	not derived (see "Recommendation")
Biological guidance value (BGV)	not derived (see "Recommendation")
Occupational exposure limit (OEL)	not derived (see "Recommendation")
ADL	see Annex (December 2019)
Health surveillance group	if possible, surveillance; for acute and chronic effects, a health surveillance is recommended (see text)

BGV:
AAVal (Hb adducts): 80
µmol/g globin (for non-smokers)

ECMA, 2019. *Guidance on information requirements and chemical safety assessment Appendix to Chapter R.8: Guidance for preparing a scientific report for health based exposure limits at the workplace.*

BLV:
 Biological reference value → percentile 95 in a general population of adults or by default in a control population not occupationally exposed

DFG - Germany

Since the end of the 1980s

- ☐ **EKA¹**: Exposure Equivalent for Carcinogenic substances
 - ✓ MAK value available
 - ✓ Based on the relationships between the concentration of the carcinogen in the workplace air and that of the substance or its metabolites in biological material
- ☐ **BLW²**: Biological guidance value
 - ✓ From non-carcinogenic effects of carcinogenic substances and for substances without sufficient data
 - ✓ The BLW values are intended to advance this aim by providing a basis for biomonitoring of exposed persons by the physician.
 - ✓ Risk of health impairment cannot be excluded
- ☐ **BAR³**: for non-carcinogenic effects of carcinogenic substances and for substances without sufficient data
 - ✓ Background level in a reference population of adults (working age) not occupationally exposed to the substance.
 - ✓ Based on the 95th percentile of the distribution

¹ Expositionäquivalente für krebserzeugende Arbeitsstoffe

² Biologisch Leitwerte

³ Biologische Arbeitsstoff-Referenzwerte

DFG (German Research Foundation): List of MAK and BAT Values 2020. Reimann/Senate Commission for the investigation of health hazards of chemical compounds in the work. Report 95. German Medical Science. 2020. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7040406/>

DFG - Derivation of Biological values – EKA

1,3-butadiene
CLP classification:
H340 (Muta.1B)
H350 (Carc.1A)

DFG - Derivation of Biological values – BLW

- **Biomarkers**: haemoglobin adduct of acrylamide in blood (AAVal) → N-(2-carbonamideethyl)valine
- No correlation between the air and the AAVal level in blood (derivation EKA values not possible)
- **Effect**: neurotoxic effects
- **Key study**: Hagmar et al. (2001)
- **POD**: 14.6 µg/L blood of AAVal
- **BLW = 15 µg/L blood of AAVal**

Acrylamide
CLP classification:
H340 (Muta.1B)
H350 (Carc.1B)

ACGIH - USA

Since the end of the 1980s

- 1st step: Feasibility assessment
- 2nd step: if sufficient scientific evidence BEI (Biological Exposure Index) development
- No BEI on non threshold effects
- For carcinogenic substances:
 - ✓ BEI derived if other effects occur
 - ✓ BEI based on TLV-TWA (8h-OEL)

Conclusion

	HBM4EU	SCOEL/RAC	ANSES	DFG	ACGIH
Values	HBM-GV _{GenPop} HBM-GV _{worker}	BIV No Value for non threshold effect BGV	BIV Pragmatic BLV BRV	BLW EKA BAR	BEI No BEI for non threshold effect
Option 1	GenPop: No HBM-GV_{GenPop} Workers: RA: 10 ⁻⁶ , 10 ⁻⁵ and 10 ⁻⁴		RA: 10 ⁻⁶ , 10 ⁻⁵ and 10 ⁻⁴	LKA (correlation with MAK values)	BEI based on correlation with TLV TWA
Option 2	GenPop: No HBM-GV_{GenPop} Workers: HBM-GV _{worker} based on an other effect		Pragmatic BIV based on an other effect	BLW	BEI based on an other effect
Background option	Not in task 5.2	BGV	BRV	BAR	No

1/3/2017

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Discussion

How risk managers can use these values (based on excess risk) for workers ?

- ✓ Based on RA
- ✓ Based on an other effect

Could these approaches also be applied for the general population ?

How could threshold for biomarkers of effect (genotoxic or carcinogenic) be an additional option ?

7.6 Biomarker and matrix selection

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HBM guidance values
WP 5, Task 5.2

Biomarker and matrix selection
F. Lamkarkach (ANSES), J-P. Antignac (INRAE), M. Mengelers (RIVM)

Biomarkers – some definitions

- Biomarker of exposure: parent substance, or one of its metabolites, determined in a biological matrix, consistently linked to exposure
- Biomarker of effect: "any measurable biochemical, physiological or other alteration within an organism that, depending on magnitude, can be recognized as an established or potential health impairment or disease"
- Biomarkers of susceptibility: "effect-modifying factors, including both genetic (e.g., genetic polymorphisms of drug metabolizing and DNA repair enzymes) and acquired conditions"


```

graph LR
    Exposure[exposure] --> ID[Internal dose]
    ID --> BED[Biologically effective dose]
    BED --> EBE[Early biological effect]
    EBE --> AF[Altered function]
    AF --> Disease[Disease]
    SM[Susceptibility markers] --> EBE
    
```

Annex 2014 adapted from P. Manoni et al. / Toxicology Letters 168 (2007) 210–218

Biomarkers – criteria

- Specificity
- Sensitivity
- Influenced by confounding factors (e.g. sex, smoking, alcohol consumption)
- Toxicokinetics
- Available data:
 - ✓ on relationship between exposure and biological level
 - ✓ on relationship between effects and biological level and
- Directly relevant of the mode of action
- LOQ/LOD
- Stability in the matrix

Some examples of selection of biomarkers (HBM-GVs)

	List of relevant/identified biomarkers	Selected BME for the general population and workers		Criteria of exclusion/selection
DBP	MBP, MCPPE and MHBP in urine	Total MBP in urine		Specificity Available data
DEHP	MEHP, 5OH-MEHP, 5oxo-MEHP 5cx-MEPP and 2cx-MMHP in urine	<i>GenPop:</i> Adults ≥ [5 oxo-MEHP and 5-OH-MEHP] in urine	<i>Workers:</i> 5x-MEPP in urine	Specificity Available data Variability Toxicokinetics and toxicological aspects Excretion rate
Cd	Cd in urine and Cd in blood	<i>GenPop:</i> U-Cd	<i>Workers:</i> U-Cd and B-Cd	Specificity Available data on relationship between effects and biomarker Invasiveness (B-Cd)
DMF	DMF in urine, MCVal in blood, AMCC in urine, Formamide, total NMI (NMF+NHNMF)	total NMI in urine AMCC in urine	-	Specificity Available data on relationship with effects Available data on correlation with air Directly link to MoA (AMCC) Invasiveness (MCVal)

Dealing with conjugated phase II metabolites (glucuronides, sulfates...)

Analytical method

Without deconjugation

Measurement of the « free » (usually biologically active) form *

Meaningful from toxicological / environmental health points of view

Simplified sample preparation then less interlaboratory variability

Facilitated methodological harmonization

Sensitivity issue in case of lowest abundance/proportion of the free form in the considered sample type

With deconjugation

Quantification of the total (free + deconjugated) forms

Aggregated indicator of the internal dose, protective / meaningful value for exposure assessment

More interlaboratory variability in terms of deconjugation techniques and need for controlled deconjugation efficiency, limiting harmonization

Optimal sensitivity and approach for lowest concentrated markers

* Separate measurement of the conjugated forms possible (LC-MS/MS or LC-HRMS) but less commonly implemented in laboratories and BME identification / quantifications issues.

Point of discussion

- What is the reasoning to select a biomarker
 - Are there preferred criteria (referring to the list of criteria) ?
 - More than one biomarker: what are the advantages and disadvantages ?

- Different analytical and toxicological preference(s) for selection
 - Is it a trade-off between analysis and toxicology?

Selection of matrix – criteria

- Matrix should have no effect on chemical stability of biomarker
- Variability of the matrix should not have an effect on the biomarker
- Matrix should not affect inter- and intra-variability of biomarker
- Timed sampling or not ?
 - Urine (morning, before and after work, 24h, spot)
 - Blood (timing could be important)
- Specification of blood sample
 - Whole blood, serum, plasma, erythrocytes
- Urine sample
 - Correction for diuresis ? How ?
- Choice to be based on toxicokinetics of biomarker ?
- Matrix should be (more or less) indicative of exposure duration

Matrix selection – Urine

1- Mass balance equations

Situation 1: the selected BM is the parent compound

$$HBM\ GV = \frac{TW \cdot F_{M(substance)}}{\text{Daily urinary flow rate adjusted to bw}}$$

Situation 2: the selected BM is a relevant metabolite

$$HBM\ GV = \frac{TW \cdot \left[\frac{MW_{(metab)} \cdot F_{M(metab)}}{MW_{(substance)}} \right]}{\text{Daily urinary flow rate adjusted to bw}}$$

Situation 3: the selected BMs are two relevant metabolites

$$HBM\ GV = \frac{TW \cdot \left[\frac{MW_{(metab1)} \cdot F_{M(metab1)} + MW_{(metab2)} \cdot F_{M(metab2)}}{MW_{(substance)}} \right]}{\text{Daily urinary flow rate adjusted to bw}}$$

Reid P, Robinson C, Lister B, Shostak F, Adams-Cook B, Dwyer T (2013) Urine creatinine correction (UcrCr) (HBM-GVs) – Strategy to derive human biomonitoring guidelines using HBM-GVs for health risk assessment. International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health 220, 1112-122

Daily urine volume adjusted to the BW

Amounts of body weight standardized urine

- children: 30 ml/kg bw/d
- adults: 20 ml/kg bw/d

* Children: 33.4 ml/kg bw/d (age 3) to 20.5 ml/kg bw/d (adolescents, age <15y)
Adults: average 20 ml/kg bw/d (15-80y)

*Kivimäki L, Ripa SM, Vuorio A, Devereux AJ, St-Amant A, Norg A (2015) Standardizing Equivalents for Interpretation of Urinary Fluoride. Regul Toxicol Pharmacol. 72(1): 158-67 doi: 10.1016/j.rtp.2015.04.002

- High coefficient of variation (100%)
- Pregnant women are not covered
- New data indicate a higher urinary flow rate

Urinary flow rate (some references)

Norwegian study (N=49) 2020				
	Total urine (ml/24h)	Total (ml/kg bw/24h)	Male (ml/kg bw/24h)	Female (ml/kg bw/24h)
min	995	11.7	11.7	15.0
p05	1068	14.5	13.4	15.7
median	1980	29.1	24.9	31.0
p95	3613	49.0	36.7	54.9
max	4210	52.0	55.4	62.0
mean (SD)	2085 (744)	29 (11)	26 (9)	32 (11)

Swiss study 2010-2011				
	SES men N=950	SES women N=987	SEPOGH men N=475	SEPOGH women N=523
Age (SD) y	48.1 (17.2)	46.2 (16.8)	47.0 (17.6)	47.8 (16.7)
Weight (SD) kg	81.7 (16.7)	66.3 (13.2)	81.5 (13.9)	65.4 (12.6)
Volume of urine ml/24h	1928 (876)	2072 (922)	1698 (756)	1719 (702)
Urinary flow rate ml/kg/24h	23.6	31.3	20.8	26.3
Urinary creatinine excretion (umol/24h)	15620 (3706)	9921 (2518)	15651 (3415)	10273 (2183)
Urinary creatinine excretion (umol/kg/24h)	100 (43)	151 (38)	194 (42)	161 (40)

SES: Swiss Survey on Salt: a cross-sectional, population-based survey including people of 15-years and older; SEPOGH: Swiss Kidney Project on Genes in Hypertension: an independent, population-based study

NHANES 2014		
	24h urine (based on two 24h samples) N=256	24h urine (based on one 24h sample) N=391
Sex	225 m - 231 f	195 m - 195 f
Age (SD) y	44.7 (14.2)	43.2 (14.3)
Volume, unweighted mean (SD), ml	1884 (1067)	1850 (1088)
Volume, weighted mean (95%CI), ml	1919 (1776-2064)	1829 (1739-2110)
Creatinine, unweighted mean (SD) mg	1543 (570)	1568 (572)
Creatinine weighted mean (CI), mg	1568 (1513-1623)	1547 (1419-1675)

Matrix selection – Urine

Context:

- ✓ 24 (or 48) hour collection of urine is laborious and (to some extent) unreliable in large epidemiological studies
- ✓ Morning or spot urine: concentrations of chemicals in urine may vary (within 1 person) from void to void because of dose, dosing interval, kinetics and urinary flow rate...
- ✓ Concentrated or diluted urine: uncorrected concentrations in urine may not be representative for (daily) exposure

Main methods of correction:

Creatinine

- Frequently applied because of its (almost) constant urinary excretion by glomerular filtration (~ 85%) and active, tubular secretion (~ 15%).
- Analysis: routine by an automated colorimetric method. "Range": 0.3 - 3 g/l

Specific gravity

- Alternative method measuring the ratio of the density (= mass of a unit volume) of a substance with that of water (= relative density).
- Analysis: routine by refractometer. No dimension. "Range": 1.002 - 1.03

Osmolality

- Sparingly applied method measuring a solution's osmotic pressure.
- Analysis: routine by osmometer. Unity: osmol/kg. No "range" defined

Advantages and disadvantages of 3 correction methods

Method	Advantage	Disadvantage
Creatinine	- Simple method - Most popular, much experience, good for comparison (?)	- Dependent of age, gender, race, meat consumption + many other factors
Osmolality	- Simple method	- Least popular - Dependent of glycosuria (diabetes) and proteinuria (CKD)
Specific Gravity	- Simple method - Becoming popular	- Less dependent of age, gender and race, etc. but dependent of glycosuria (diabetes) and proteinuria (CKD)

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Point of discussion

Daily urine production

- ✓ Should default values be revised (taking uncertainty into account) ?

Correction for diuresis

- ✓ Should correction for diuresis always be investigated (compare corrected vs uncorrected) ?
- ✓ Methods for correction (established versus potential) ?

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Questions for the subgroup discussion

1

- What is the reasoning to select a biomarker**
 - More than one biomarker: what are the advantages and disadvantages ?
 - Different analytical and toxicological preference(s) for selection: Is it a trade-off between analysis and toxicology?

- Correction for diuresis**
 - Should correction for diuresis always be investigated (compare corrected vs uncorrected) ? AND Methods for correction (established versus potential) ?

2

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Questions for the subgroup discussion – additional

- What is the reasoning to select a biomarker**
 - ✓ Are there preferred criteria (referring to the list of criteria) ?

- Daily urine production**
 - ✓ Should default values be revised (taking uncertainty into account) ?

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**Thank you very
much
for your attention!**

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7.7 How to improve the setting of levels of confidence associated to HBM-GVs?

HBM4EU project – WP 5 - TASK 5.2 – Workshop

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How to improve the setting of *levels of confidence* associated to HBM-GVs ?

Fatoumata Sissoko

Levels of confidence associated to HBM-GVs *Summary*

Aim : reflect the uncertainties related to the derivation of HBM-GVs

1. Overview of different bodies approaches
2. Criteria for the setting of levels of confidence
3. Levels of confidence attributed to the derived HBM-GVs : some examples
4. Discussion

November 2020

1. Overview of different bodies approaches

Organization	Proposed levels	Criteria
US EPA (TRV with a threshold level)	High / Medium / Low	- Database - Key study - Dedicated chapter
US EPA (TRV without threshold level)	Description of the strengths and weaknesses	Description in the chapter « Discussion of confidence »
OEHHA (Cal-EPA)	Description of the strengths and weaknesses of the TRV addressed in a dedicated chapter	
ATSDR	No level of confidence given, but discussion	
Health Canada	High / Moderate / Low Possibility to combine levels	Description in a dedicated chapter
RIVM	High / Medium / Low	Judgment of experts which implies: - Quality of the study - Duration of the study - Data - Consensus between experts
WHO/IPCS	High / Moderate / Low	Description in the chapter « Uncertainties in the evaluation of health risks »
Anses date	High / Moderate / Low Possibility to combine levels	Collective expertise - nature and quality of the data - critical effect and mode of action - key study - critical dose

2. Criteria for the setting of levels of confidence

- Individual criteria are examined and they are given a confidence level:
 - high,
 - medium,
 - low
- By equally combining individual criteria , an overall level of confidence is attributed

- The option chosen for deriving the HBM-GV will directly influence the overall level of confidence attributed:
 - as human data are considered more reliable over animal studies, HBM-GVs derived by option 1 will have higher levels of confidence than HBM-GVs derived by option 2 or 3.
- Levels of confidence are relying on expert judgment.

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2. *Criteria for the setting of levels of confidence*

- **Nature and quality of the data**

- Epidemiological and/or toxicological studies available should cover many different effects, exposure times and exposure windows.
- Studies conducted in humans are preferred over animal studies.
- If there should be only a few animal studies or if available animal studies should be conducted only on a single species, then the level of confidence would be low or medium at best.

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2. Criteria for the setting of levels of confidence

- **Choice of the critical effect and the mode of action**
 - The likelihood of the transferability of the critical effect (as well as the MOA) from animal species to humans will be given a level of confidence (for the duration and route of exposure considered).
- **Key study**
 - Quality of the study
 - ✓ key epidemiological study : several tools e.g. OHAT approach, Biomonitoring Environmental epidemiology and short lived chemicals (BEES-C)

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✓ Key animal study: tools as e.g. ToxRtool or Scirap

2. Criteria for the setting of levels of confidence

- **Choice of the critical dose (POD)**
 - Using a BMDL > NOAEL/LOAEL pair > a single LOAEL or NOAEL
 - Quality of the dose-response relationship
 - ✓ possibly depending on the number of doses tested in the study
 - ✓ difference in concentration between the doses tested.
- **Extrapolations across and within species**
 - Using a quality PBTK model to extrapolate a TRV (or a POD) is considered more reliable than the use of default values accounting for intra- and inter-species extrapolations

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2. *Criteria for the setting of levels of confidence*

- **2 main elements for assessing the confidence :**

- Understanding of the relationship between the measured biomarker and the critical or relevant target tissue dose metric
- Robustness of the available pharmacokinetic models and data.

3. Levels of confidence attributed to the derived HBM-GVs : overview

Substance	Subpopulation	Derivation method	Global LoC
DEHP	GenPop	Based on a TDI (option 2)	Medium
	Workers	Based on an animal POD (option 3)	
DINCH	GenPop	Based on a TDI (option 2)	Medium
DnBP	GenPop	Based on a DNEL (option 2)	Medium
	Workers	Based on an animal POD (option 3)	
DiBP	GenPop	Based on a DNEL (option 2)	Low
	Workers	Based on an animal POD for DnBP (option 3)	

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3. Levels of confidence attributed to the derived HBM-GVs : overview

Substance	Subpopulation	Derivation method	Global LoC
BBzP	GenPop	Based on an animal POD (option 3)	Medium
	Workers	Based on an animal POD (option 3)	
DPHP	GenPop	Based on a RfD (option 2)	Low
	Workers	Based on an animal POD (option 3)	
BPA	GenPop	Based on a provisional TDI (option 2)	Medium
BPS	GenPop/Workers	Based on an animal POD (option 3)	Medium/Low
Cadmium	GenPop	Based on a relation between health effects and biomarker concentration (option 1)	High
	Workers		High/Medium
NMP	Medium/Low	Based on an animal POD(option 3)	Medium
NEP	Medium/Low	Based on an animal POD(option 3)	Medium/Low

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3. Levels of confidence attributed to the derived HBM-GVs : example DIBP (general population)

- **Nature and quality of DiBP epidemiological and/or toxicological data:**
 - very limited database on human studies, mostly oral rodent studies;
 - no toxicity studies on low dose area (below 100 mg/kg bw/d) for which effects can't be excluded
 - only one TK study (oral) with one volunteer → **low**
- **Critical endpoint and mode of action:**
 - high confidence in MoA (anti-androgenic effects)
 - evidence for these effects in humans is available → **high**
- **Key study and POD:**
 - Same as DnBP was identified and based on a read across approach, a potency difference factor of 25% was applied to obtain a LOAEL for DiBP → **low**
- **inter- and intra-species extrapolations:** default assessment factors → **low**

Global level of confidence for the DiBP HBM-GVs in the general population is set to 'low'.

Date

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3. Levels of confidence attributed to the derived HBM-GVs : example of cadmium (workers)

Derivation method	Based on a relationship between U-Cd and markers of renal effects
Species	Human (workers)
Route/type of study	Inhalation (and oral route)
Exposure duration	Long-term exposure
Critical endpoint	Renal toxicity

- **Nature and quality of epidemiological and/or toxicological data:**
 - Large database → **high**
- **Critical endpoint and mode of action:**
 - Evidence of effects on the renal function is high
 - critical endpoint is supported by the clinical interpretation of markers of renal toxicity → **high**
- **Key study and POD:**
 - the study was conducted in humans at the workplace, in a large population
 - But , the average age of workers was 45 years (+/- 10 years) (less protection to young workers)
 - → **medium**

→ Global level of confidence for U-Cd HBM-GV in the occupational field: "high/medium"

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4. Discussion

- Attributing low levels of confidence can highlight the data gaps → **accuracy of the value** .
 - However, a low level of confidence does not necessarily mean a low level of protection, because the HBM-GV derivation is generally based on very conservative scenarios and default assumptions → **conservative value**
- ***Is it necessary to consider these 2 dimensions for the attribution of the confidence level?***
- Can we consider a probabilistic approach for the derivation of HBM-GVs (with a distribution of parameters)?

**Thank you
for your attention**

Investigate, evaluate, protect

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 733032.

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7.8 Toxicokinetics and modelling aspects

T5.2 - Workshop on the refinement of the methodology for the HBM-GVs derivation
November 4th - 6th - ANSES (virtual meeting)

Third sub-group work session :

Points of discussion in connection with toxicokinetics and modelling considerations when calculating the HBM-GVs

Eva Ougier

1

T5.2 - Workshop on the refinement of the methodology for the HBM-GVs derivation
November 4th - 6th - ANSES (virtual meeting)

III - Points of discussion in connection with toxicokinetics and modelling considerations when calculating the HBM-GVs

Presentation of the points of discussion

- 1 - Assumption of a steady-state exposure in using the mass balance approach
- 2 - Value of the urinary excretion factor (F_{ue})
- 3 - Exposure pattern when estimating the concentration of the exposure biomarker corresponding to an external exposure guidance value

2

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Preliminary information : urinary mass balance equation

For a single biomarker of exposure (metabolite)

$$\text{HBM - GV} = \frac{\text{TRV or TRV - like value} \cdot \left[\frac{(\text{MW Metabolite}) \cdot (\text{Fue Metabolite})}{\text{MW Parent compound}} \right]}{\text{average daily urinary flow rate adjusted to bw}}$$

For two biomarkers of exposure (metabolites)

$$\text{HBM - GV} = \frac{\text{TRV or TRV - like value} \cdot \left[\frac{(\text{MW Metabolite 1} \cdot \text{Fue Metabolite 1}) + (\text{MW Metabolite 2} \cdot \text{Fue Metabolite 2})}{\text{MW Parent compound}} \right]}{\text{average daily urinary flow rate adjusted to bw}}$$

with : TRV = toxicity reference value; TRV-like value : application of AFs to a selected animal POD
 MW = molecular weight;
 Fue = proportional urinary excretion factor ;
 bw = body weight

3

○ **1st point of discussion: steady-state assumption in using the mass balance approach**

The use of a mass balance approach for estimating urinary concentration(s) of selected exposure biomarker(s) consistent with an external exposure guidance value implies to **assume a steady-state exposure**.

However, in case of short-half life substances as phthalates or BPA, steady-state is potentially not reached considering the exposure pattern of the general population.

➤ **What impact could this have on the derived HBM-GV value?**

4

○ **2nd point of discussion: parameters possibly influencing the F_{ue}: 24h or 48h?**

Should the F_{ue} estimated at 24h or at 48h be used preferably, considering that:

- when the selected TRV is e.g. a TDI, the dose is given *per day* (e.g. µg/kg bw/day)
- a *daily* urinary flow rate adjusted to the bw is the denominator of the mass balance equation?

Compound	Selected biomarker of exposure	Elimination half-life of metabolite (hour)	F _{ue}		Key PK study
			24h after exposure to the parent compound	48h after exposure to the parent compound	
DEHP	5-oxo-MCHP	10	0.109	0.113	Anderson et al., 2011
	5-OH-MEHP	10	0.149	0.156	
	5-cx-MCHP	12-15	0.132	0.139	
DINCH	OH-MINCH	9.5-10	0.096	0.107	Koch et al., 2013
	cx-MINCH	16.5-18	0.017	0.020	

○ **2rd point of discussion: other parameters possibly influencing the F_{ue}**

How to assess the potential variability of the F_{ue} of the selected exposure biomarker(s), depending on the inter-individual characteristics between the PK study volunteers and the target population (e.g. age, gender, differences in metabolism)?

Compound	Key PK study	N	Volunteers characteristic (age range, gender, body weight...)	Oral dose	Mean F _{ue} (at 24h) of selected exposure biomarker	F _{ue} considered for the HBM-GV derivation
BBzP	Anderson et al., 2001	7	Not specified	High dose	0.78 (SD: 0.39) (MBzP)	0.73
				Low dose	0.67 (SD: 0.26) (MBzP)	
	Koch et al. 2012	1	Male, 36 years, 87 kg	~60 µg/kg	0.84 (MnBP)	-
DnBP	Anderson et al., 2001	8	Not specified	High dose (510 µg)	0.73 (MnBP)	0.69
		8		Low dose (225 µg)	0.64 (MnBP)	
DiBP	Koch et al. 2012	1	Male, 36 years, 87 kg	~60 µg/kg	0.71 (MiBP)	0.70

○ **2nd point of discussion: other parameters possibly influencing the F_{ue}**

- Molar excretion fractions of DPHP(-d4) metabolites at about 24 h (% of the oral dose administered)

Metabolite	Excretion at 24 h, Leng et al. (2014) [%]	Excretion at 22 h, Klein et al. (2018) [%]	Mean calculated excretion at about 24 h [%]
OH-MPHP	9.91 ± 3.45	2.03 ± 1.23	5.97
Oxo-MPHP	12.61 ± 3.90	3.28 ± 3.63	7.95
cx-MPHP	0.42 ± 0.11	0.095 ± 0.116	0.26

○ **3th point of discussion:**

➤ Which exposure pattern should be assumed when estimating the concentration of the exposure biomarker corresponding to an external exposure guidance value?

BPA example

t-TDI of 4 µg/kg bw/d

Forward PBTK modelling
considering a constant 24h-
averaged exposure

Free BPA plasmatic concentration :
6.8.10⁻³ µg/L (0.03 nmol/L)

Urinary total BPA concentration :
233 µg/L (1022 nmol/L)

- Key study : Tyl et al., 2008
- Critical effect : increased relative mean kidney weight in F0 adult mice
- Mice exposed throughout the day to BPA (BPA-containing feed in feeding jars)

However, as the major source of BPA exposure is through diet in the general population, the most likely exposure pattern are peaks of exposure corresponding to the meals.

➤ Thus should the dose corresponding to t-TDI be better fractionned into peaks of exposure?

t-TDI of 4 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}/\text{d}$

Forward PBTK modelling
considering peaks of exposure?

Free BPA plasmatic concentration:
mean value? C_{max} (peak value)?

Urinary total BPA concentration:
mean value? C_{max} (peak value)?

Warning, here simulations considering:
- 3 daily intakes of 1.2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ (meals)
- 2 dermal intakes of 0.2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$

BPA example: derivation of the HBM-GV_{worker}

oral worker DNEL of 8
 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}/\text{d}$

Forward PBTK modelling (considering a 24h-averaged constant oral exposure)
100% oral exposure
⇒ AUC of free BPA/total BPA ratio ~ 1%

Free BPA in plasma:
 $13.6 \cdot 10^{-3} \mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ (0.06 nmol/L)
Total urinary BPA:
460 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ (2030 nmol/L)

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III - Points of discussion in connection with toxicokinetics and modelling considerations when calculating the HBM-GVs

Questions for the subgroups discussions

- 1 – Is the assumption of a steady-state exposure correct when using the mass balance approach? If not what could be a better approach?**
- 2 – How to select the best value for the urinary excretion factor (F_{ue})? 24h or 48h? male and/or females, ages? How to express uncertainties around this factor?**
- 3- Which exposure pattern should be considered when estimating the internal concentration of the biomarker corresponding to an external exposure guidance value**

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7.9 Occupational Biomonitoring activity for OECD Working Party on Hazard Assessment (WPHA) and Working Party on Exposure Assessment (WPEA) & collaboration with ISES Europe HBM group

Eidgenössisches Departement für Wirtschaft, Bildung und Forschung WBF
Staatsekretariat für Wirtschaft SECO
Resort für Chemikalien und Arbeit ARECH

Occupational Biomonitoring activity for OECD Working Party on Hazard Assessment (WPHA) and Working Party on Exposure Assessment (WPEA) & collaboration with ISES Europe HBM group

Co-authors: Robert Pasanen-Kase (SECO), Nancy Hopf (Unisanté), Tiina Santonen (FIOH), Jos Bessems (VITO), Peter Kujath (BAuA) & Maryam Zare Jeddi (ISES Europe)

HBM4EU- Workshop on the refinement of the methodology for the HBM-GVs derivation, November 4th-6th, 2020 – ANSES (virtual meeting)

Some reasons for Occupational Biomonitoring

- Biomonitoring can address multiple exposures and health risks of dangerous substances at workplaces.
- Many substances cannot be assessed only by air measurements and limit values, e.g. having a skin notation and/or dermal uptake.
- Health and productivity of workers are important resources which should be protected in an efficient and sustainable way.
- The current existing biomonitoring guidance is fragmented in different national guidances and no harmonised biomonitoring guidance exists.

∑ Motivation for bringing OECD key experts together to develop a common biomonitoring guidance and recommendation.

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Working together with 40 institutes/ organisations for a 3 year work programme

- ACC (American Chemistry Council), US
- ANSES (French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety), FR
- ARC (Arnot Research & Consulting), CAN
- BAuA, The Federal Institute for Occupational Safety and Health, DE
- BASF, DE
- Belgium DG Environment, BE
- BfR (German Federal Institute for risk assessment), DE
- BIAAC (Business at OECD)
- CEFIC (The European Chemical Industry Council), EU
- Covestro, DE
- Currenca, DE
- DFG Germany (German Research Foundation), DE
- ECHA (European Chemicals Agency), EU
- ESTeSL (Escola Nacional de Saúde Pública, Universidade Nova de Lisboa), PT
- EU-OSHA (European Agency for Safety and Health at Work), EU
- ExxonMobil Biomedical Sciences, US
- FIOH (Finnish Institute of Occupational Health), FI
- Health Canada, CA
- HSE (Health and Safety Executive), UK
- IfADo, Leibniz Research Centre for Working Environment, DE
- INRS (Reference body for occupational risk prevention in France), FR
- ISES Europe (Europe Regional Chapter of the international Society of Exposure Science), EU
- Japan MHLW (Ministry of Health Labour and Welfare), JP
- Japan National Institute of Occupational Safety and Health, JP
- JRC (Joint Research Centre), EU
- Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, BE
- KI (Karolinska Institutet), SE
- National Health Laboratory Luxembourg, LU
- Orthoanalytik GmbH, CH
- RIVM (National Institute for Public Health and Environment), NL
- SECO (State Secretariat for Economic Affairs), CH
- Shell, NL
- Swedish Chemicals Agency, SE
- Swiss FOPH (Federal Office of Public Health), CH
- SUVA (Swiss National Accident Insurance Fund), CH
- UBA (German Environment Agency), DE
- Unisanté (Center for Primary Care and Public Health), CH
- University Zurich, CH
- US-EPA (United States Environmental Protection Agency), US
- VITO NV, BE

Defining together primary 7 aims

- a. **Compare existing methods in deriving OBL (Occupational Biomonitoring Levels)** for selected substances of high concern, including European Substances of High Concern (SVHC) candidate substances.
- b. **Identify data gaps and future research needs** with regard to regulatory use of biomarkers of exposure data.
- c. **Propose quality criteria and minimum requirements** for OBLs, provisional OBLs and monitoring, including toxicokinetic data, providing discussion of variance and uncertainty and procedural aspects of quality management.
- d. **Building upon these cases as well as available current guidance**, to elaborate concrete **general tiered guidance** on the derivation of OBL with respect to accepted points of departure in risk assessment.
- e. **Propose different OBL derivation methods** for screening purposes and for more advanced regulatory risk assessment contexts.
- f. **Recommend general biomonitoring options** in occupational settings taking into account cost-effectiveness and various risk management options.
- g. **Provide a characterization and outlook for the use of effect-based biomarker monitoring** for substances or substance groups with a relevant mode of action. The results of this can be useful for addressing co-exposures and relevant mixture effects in the future.

Work sharing in 7 subtasks

Subtask No	Name	Main contact points
1	Project coordination	Robert
2	OBL derivation and methodologies	Tiina
3	Provisional OBL derivation and methodologies	Nancy and Robert
4	Effect-biomarker characterisation and recommendation	Nancy and Robert
5	Monitoring guidance including ethics and reporting	Peter
6	Tiered approaches & terminology	Jos
7	Guidance writing	Tiina

Defining together usable terminologies

Change from **Biomonitoring Derived No Effect Levels (BDNEL)**
to
Occupational Biomonitoring Levels (OBL)

We can now provide a useful meaning for the updated terminology.
In parallel we have started discussing terminologies for the tiered approach
at 5th October with the co-leads and French colleagues
in subtask 6 → Lead: Jos Bessems, VITO, BE

Intentions of subtask 6: Tiered approach

If we cannot elaborate a (refined) OBL because there are insufficient toxicological or epidemiological data, what can we do to help the industrial hygienist and the occupational physician? What can we put in the toolbox to bring health surveillance to a higher level and to control workplace exposure using occupational biomonitoring?

The answer is, a set of occupational exposure levels with expressed as precautionary, more worst-case lower tier OBLs, partly health-based, partly based on levels found in the general population and partly based on what is technically achievable at the workplace:

Aiming to allow to make more efficient use of occupational biomonitoring measurement data

Tiers without fears- current discussion status

<u>Exposure</u>		<u>Effects</u>		<u>Level</u>	<u>If exceeded?</u>
Term	Tier	Term	Tier		
OBL	4	OBEL	3	Refined	Health risk indicated
POBL	3	POBEL	2	Provisional	Health risk maybe indicated
ROBL	2	ROBEL	1	Reference	Occupational exposure indicated
TOBL	1			Technical	Exposure indicated

Focus and selection of 4 case studies for subtask 2 and 3

Reducing complexity

Requirements for a good substance candidate:

1. Toxicological concern
2. Workplace relevance
3. Data availability for DNEL derivations
4. Biomonitoring suitability
5. existing guidance or limit values availability

Let us take a look on our candidate proposals

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Outcome 30th September, focus with broad toxicological concern

No	substance (CAS)	toxicological relevance	workplace relevance	expected data availability	biomonitoring suitability	DNEL, guidance or limit values	Overall judgement score
2b	HDI, Hexamethylen-1,6-disocyanat (B22-06-0)	++	+(+)	++	+	+	7.5+
3	Chrome VI (diverse CAS-No)	++	++	++	++	++	10+
5b	DEHP, Bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (117-81-7)	++	(+), trend decreasing	+(+)	+/-	+	5+
6	Aluminium (7429-90-5)	-?, depending on neurotoxicity data	++	+	+	+	4+

We selected sensitising, carcinogenic, endocrine disruptive and reproduction toxic plus potentially neurotoxic substances

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Experience sharing in subtask 2 & 3

Example 1

Development of a data collection template for subtasks 2 and 3

Example 2

Experience sharing for compiling and evaluating data is ongoing

	Case studies			
	Aluminium	Chrome	HDI	DEHP
Expert I for data collection	Farida Lamkarkach and colleagues, FR and Devika Poddalgoda, CAN	Susana Viegas, PT	Gabriele Leng and colleagues, DE	Nancy Hopf, CH
Expert II for data collection	Thomas Göen, DE	Farida Lamkarkach, FR	Sven Hoffmann, CH	Tiina Santonen, FIN
Expert III for data collection		Michael Koller, CH		

So far we received datasets for Al, Cr, HDI and for DEHP, which can be used now for derivation method comparisons.

Rationale and motivation for P(rovisional)OBL-subtask 3 (led by Nancy Hopf & Robert Pasanen, CH)

- Biomonitoring can address multiple exposures and health risks of dangerous substances at workplaces.
- Most of the chemicals covered under REACH have limited registration datasets depending on their tonnage. Nevertheless some of them are toxic and can pose a risk to workers via dermal or oral exposure. For many of them a NOAEL is available.
- For these chemicals methods to derive a provisional Occupational Biomonitoring Levels (OBL) could be suitable for a risk identification at workplace and for checking the suitability of personal safety equipment and training at work places or for a refined OBL derivation.

A quick & sensitive provisional approach is needed to be able to cope with numerous substances and limited dataset availabilities.

Currently tested & discussed NOAEL urinary fraction approach- first results are promising...

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Subtask 2 (led by Tiina Santonen, FIOH)

- Overview on existing schemes for deriving health-based biomonitoring limit or guidance values- **done**
- combining case study datasets of experts by co leads- **done**
- Application of the methods to case studies & characterisation of methods for guidance- **ongoing**
- **aim to develop a draft guidance for OBL setting, of course we are in parallel inspired by:**

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Examples: confidence scoring, use of urinary fraction data,...

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Experience sharing with international networks like ISES Europe and HBM4EU

Cross fertilisation via ISES Europe

End of January: JRC ISES Europe workshop, aiming five strategic and numerous co- publications with large expert overlap to our OECD activity. Some of the publications are related to most of our subtasks.

Working titles:

- *Biomonitoring as underused exposure assessment tool in Occupational Safety and Health context – Challenges and way forward*
- *Towards a systematic use of effect biomarkers in population and occupational biomonitoring*

Special thanks to Maryam Zare Jeddi, Susana Viegas, Jos Bessems & many other colleagues

(Contact info: maryam.zare-jeddi@ises-europe.org)

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First publication result of ISES Europe HBM group

International Journal of
Environmental Research
and Public Health

Commentary

Biomonitoring as an Underused Exposure Assessment Tool in Occupational Safety and Health Context—Challenges and Way Forward

Susana Viegas ^{1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12}, Maryam Zare Jaddi ⁴, Nancy B. Hopf ⁵, Jos Bessems ⁵, Nicole Palmen ⁷, Karen S. Galea ⁸, Kate Jones ⁹, Peter Kujath ¹⁰, Radu-Corneliu Duca ^{11,12}, Hans Verhagen ^{11,12}, Tiina Santonen ¹⁰ and Robert Pasanen-Kase ¹⁰

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Thanks to **Susana Viegas** for efficient knowledge management in and beyond ISES Europe

8 of 12 co-authors are also active in OECD activity.... Some of them also in HBM4EU

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Effect-biomarker publication aims

Effect-biomarker are the only methods to address known and unknown mixture effects & risks in a direct way.

Aims:

- Provide an overview of available effect biomarkers for monitoring chemical exposures in the general and occupational populations
- Highlight their potential in monitoring humans exposed to chemical mixtures
- Discuss the role of
 - the adverse outcome pathway (AOP) framework
 - physiologically based kinetic and dynamic (PBK/D) modelling
 - regulatory risk assessments
 in strengthening the understanding of the biological mechanism of effect biomarkers

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Second publication:

“Towards a systematic use of effect biomarkers in population and occupational biomonitoring”

By

Maryam Zare Jeddi, Nancy B. Hopf, Susana Viegas, Anna Bal Price, Alicia Paini, Christoph van Thriel, Emilio Benfenati, Sophie Ndaw, Jos Bessems, Peter A. Behnisch, Gabriele Leng, Radu-Corneliu Duca, Hans Verhagen, Francesco Cubadda, Lorraine Brennan, Imran Ali, Arthur David, Vicente Mustieles, Mariana F. Fernandez, Henriqueta Louro, Robert Pasanen-Kase

Accepted for publication in Environment International

Bridging exposure and effect biomarkers with the AOP concept

Zare Jeddi M et al. 2020 submitted to Environmental International

Experience sharing to address mixture risks

- **Example 4 & subtask 4: prioritisation of relevant Mode of Actions (MoAs) and effect- biomarker**

No	proposed priority mode of actions /endpoints to be addressed by occupational biomonitoring	abbreviation	proposed and discussed by	Available methods as OECD guideline or DIN EN ISO standards
1	Carcinogenicity (including cancer biomarkers for genotoxicity and oxidative stress)	C (including genotox	co-leads and PT	yes
2	Mutagenicity	M	co-leads	yes
3	Reproductive toxicity	R	co-leads and FR	yes
4	Endocrine disruption	ED	co-leads	yes
5	Neurotoxicity (including acetylcholine esterase inhibition)	NT	co-leads and DE	yes
6	Developmental Neurotoxicity	DNT	JRC and co-leads	OECD GD on in vitro DNT assays is under development
7	Developmental Toxicity	DT	CAH	yes
8	Respiratory toxicity (including methemoglobin binding)	ResT	DE	yes

- 8 relevant MoAs
- mainly covered by around 20 recommended effect-biomarkers
- characterisation of methods will follow

Thanks to Maryam, Nancy, and many more colleagues promoting mixture assessments. Additionally thanks to Dan Villeneuve (US EPA) & Martin Wilks (SCAHT, CH) for promoting a follow up project to set mixture threshold levels in 2021.

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Work Environment

The screenshot shows the OECD Occupational Biomonitoring Project website. The page is titled "Occupational Biomonitoring Project" and features a navigation menu with "HOME", "ABOUT", "RESULTS", and "RESEARCH". The main content area includes a welcome message, a project work plan, and a list of subtasks. The subtasks listed are:

- Subtask 1
- Subtask 2
- Subtask 3
- Subtask 4
- Subtask 5
- Subtask 6
- Subtask 7
- Subtask 8

Thanks to OECD WPEA & WPHA for providing a good and sustainable work environment. Special thanks to Eeva Leinala & Koki Takaki.

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Subtask 5 (led by Peter Kujath, BAuA): project work sharing related to expertise

Example: Identification and characterisation of available key monitoring guidance- guideline extraction is ongoing

Shortlist of key guidelines

- **HSE_1997:** Health and Safety Executive (1997). Biological monitoring in the workplace: a guide to its practical application to chemical exposure. Sudbury, HSE Books.
- **ICPS_1993:** International Programme on Chemical Safety (IPCS) (1993). Biomarkers and risk assessment : concepts and principles. Environmental health criteria 155. Geneva, WHO.
- **WHO_1996:** WHO (1996). Biological monitoring of chemical exposure in the workplace : guidelines. - Vol. 1. Geneva
- **EC_2006:** European Commission (2006). Practical guidelines – chemical agents directive, 98/24/EC, Part II.
- **NIOSH_2018:** DeBord (2018): Application of Biological Monitoring Methods for Chemical Exposures in Occupational Health (NIOSH draft)
- **LaKind_2008:** LaKind J.S. et al (2008): Guidelines for the communication of Biomonitoring Equivalents: Report from the Biomonitoring Equivalents Expert Workshop. *Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology* 51, 516–526
- **CEN_2017:** CEN (2017): Workplace exposure — Measurement of exposure by inhalation to chemical agents — Strategy for testing compliance with occupational exposure limit values. Draft prEN 689. Last update 2017-04-25, finished version 2019 (Idea: Principles from air monitoring can be adapted to biomonitoring) Access not freely available

Subtask 5: adaptation to key needs (Peter & Co)

Starting a Guideline on application of OBLs – Outline draft for the chapter “Ethical and Legal Aspects and Reporting”

Dealing mainly with:

- Ethics and data protection in biomonitoring in occupational settings
- Providing guidance to use biomonitoring data primary in exposure assessment and health surveillance."
- Providing guidance to use biomonitoring data from health surveillance and from biomonitoring campaigns for exposure assessment.

Aiming to allow to make more efficient use of biomonitoring data.

First commenting rounds of monitoring experts are accomplished.

Thanks to Susana, Ludwine, Nancy

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Work attitude

project coordination

Aims (for all participants):

- to be constructive and motivating
- provide active knowledge exchange
- avoid redundant work
- enable compromises and majority decisions
- to stay in time and work need-oriented

We will try our best to use the available time effectively...

Suggestions

Only two main suggestions/questions for potentially missing points:

- 1) Where is the opportunity to derive provisional HBM guidance values for potential risk identification of new hazardous substances?
- 2) Is there also a role for effect-biomarker planned? They allow us to address known and unknown mixture risks and can reduce monitoring costs largely for example for phthalates and their numerous transformation products.

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Summary: current progress factors

- 1) Collaboration
- 2) Definition
- 3) Focus
- 4) Experience sharing
- 5) Work environment
- 6) Work sharing related to expertise
- 7) Work attitude

To be continued

Do you have questions, comments or interest?

**Thank you very much for your attention and for your
continous collaboration**

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